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DC Educational Development
Improving understanding of DC to DC / DC to AC conversion

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INTRODUCTION

Direct Current appears to be making a comeback, after more than a century. High Voltage DC in Transmission, Electrical Mobility, Electricity Storage with batteries, Sustainable Generation with Photo Voltaic and Solar Home Systems are some of the examples thereof. Next to the usage of DC in applications and appliances, more and

more examples are appearing that combine 'Power Electronics' / Semiconductor technology's with Digital Control to establish the so called 'DC Smart Grids' with active, soft- or firmware controlled components. That is for many quite a different approach to Electrical Engineering. So if DC is really making a comeback, what is done to educate the future generation of Electrical Engineers, to work with these technologies?

The paper proposes a method to teach and instruct the workings of power electronics and electrical drives. This method contains both a theoretical module and a practical module. The basis module is a Full-Bridge inverter, see Fig.1, that can be used to make a single phase inverter. Practical laboratory assignments for students include assembly of a single phase sinusoidal current generator and a low voltage single phase grid-tied inverter. To support the theoretical module, the foundation of the lab assignments is a newly developed Printed Circuit Board [PCB], see Fig. 2, that can be further developed into a broad variety of applications, such as DC-DC converters, DC-AC inverters and motor drives. The PCB contains four half-bridges that can be configured as 4 DC-DC converters, two Full-Bridge inverters or a three phase inverter with an additional DC-DC converter.

Fig. 1: Full bridge inverter with gate drivers and shunt resistors for current measurement. The schematic is represented by the virtual model within the green shaded area.

Fig. 2: Inverter PCB (4-half-bridges) with 2 legs with analog current and shoot through protection electronics.

To explain the aims and workings of this new PCB, a set of practical laboratory assignments was developed, with extended functionality compared to what was possible with the single phase Full Bridge inverter from Fig 1. The paper gives an overview of the possibilities of this developed PCB with the help of some typical laboratory examples meant for educational purposes.

1 MODELING DC-DC CONVERTERS

In this section we will outline the method that is used to teach the basics of the theory behind DC-DC converters. This is done by explaining the basics of the switching cell with the help of a synchronous Buck-converter[1]. Students are first learn the basics of the theory behind switched mode power supplies and to experiment with the basics of the Buck converter, a single leg of the PCB can be used.

Fig. 3: Simulation of a Synchronous Buck converter with LC filter and load on a virtual breadboard.

The output of the leg is connected to an inductor on a breadboard with output capacitor and resistive load. The control is open loop and simply taken from a signal generator, where frequency and duty cycle of the control signal can be varied. The output voltage is measured using a probe and the inductor current using a current probe and displayed in the scope. The upper trace [blue] is the output voltage, while the lower trace [red] is the inductor current. Using this configuration, students can be

taught of the DC to DC conversion as required when connecting a 20 volt USB line to a 5 volt USB line. As the circuit is built as a synchronous buck, which is analogous to a bidirectional converter, also bidirectional power flow between the input and out output can be studied.

Fig. 3 shows the simulation in Caspoc [2] of the entire setup, where the green shaded component is the PCB. Students first have to study the behaviour during simulation where they have to observe waveforms and study the influence of component parameters on the overall behaviour. Once the assignments in simulation are approved, the student can then build the circuit as firstly done virtually in the simulation in Caspoc and verify the measured actual waveforms on the oscilloscope with results from the simulation.

2 CASE STUDY GRID-TIED INVERTER

The single phase grid-tied inverter [1] is the next assignment. Here the students have to study the behaviour of a single phase inverter with analog PI control to create a sinusoidal current in phase with a sinusoidal voltage from the grid.

Fig. 4: Single phase grid-tied inverter with analog PI control and carrier oscillator circuit and coupling to the main grid via a mains transformer.

To make this assignment safe and operational for the students a low frequency transformer is used to scale the voltage down from the mains voltage towards a safer low voltage of 12 volts RMS. Here the students learn how Pulse Width Modulation [PWM] can be created using a reference voltage and a high frequency symmetrical carrier signal [1].

Fig.4 shows the simulation of the grid-tied inverter in Caspoc [2]. Besides gaining understanding on power electronics, also the importance of analog circuit design is highlighted by encouraging the students to build an effective analog control circuitry with a minimum of components. The students have to design a triangular waveform

generator using an opamp and comparator, typically an uA741 and LM311 [3]. The PI controller is built around TL082[3] and the generation of the PWM signal is performed by two comparators with pullup resistors. The outputs from the PWM-comparators are input to the gate drivers on the PCB.

From this assignment students will learn how to build a basic analog control, which is based on current measurements through shunt resistors connected between the source of the low-side mosfet and the reference ground, see fig 5.. Important is that the students understand the difficulty in following the sinusoidal voltage waveform using a PI controller. Basic concepts like gain and time constants of a PI controller as well as the current measurement and scaling is done using the two opamps inside the TL082. This simple analog approach is still possible with low frequencies like 50Hz or 60Hz, as the PI controller can track this low frequency easily. When working with three phase inverters and PI controllers for motor drives, the concepts of Field Oriented Control can be taught using a digital controller [4].

Fig. 5: Current measurement, protection and output voltage measurement of a single leg on the PCB

3 DC MOTOR CONTROLLED

Bipolar and unipolar motor control [4] can be taught using the setup from Fig. 6. Here a bipolar full bridge motor drive is displayed during simulation in Caspoc. The DC motor is connected to a flexible mechanical load. The motor current is monitored using the shunt resistors as shown in Fig. 5 and compared to a constant voltage reference. By adjusting the voltage reference, or taking a voltage reference from a laboratory signal generator, see the voltage source VSQUARE1 in fig. 6, the response of the output current can be observed. Again the students have to understand the working of an analog PI controller and the settings of the gain and time constant of the PI controller using a simple opamp [4].

The simulation in Fig. 6 shows basically the same set up as used for the single phase inverter with current control from fig. 4. The current through the motor windings is measured and compared with a square wave reference voltage. This square wave results in a change of direction in rotation as visible in the scopes in the simulation. The top scope shows the current through the motor windings, while the second scope the angular motor speed shows. The third scope shows the high frequency carrier signal.

As with the other simulation from Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, a virtual breadboard is created where components can be connected using their typical component connections. In this way students can experiment in a virtual way with connecting the components and think about physical placement of components to improve circuit layout.

Fig. 6: Permanent Magnet DC motor drive with current control

4 BRUSHLESS MOTOR DRIVE

The principle control of a Brushless motor drive is shown in Fig. 7. During the simulation the hall signals are visible and the rotor turns. Before turning to a virtual breadboard the students firstly have to understand the working of a brushless motor drive with Hall sensors. The simulation includes a basic model of a two-level inverter feeding a brushless motor. Parameters for the brushless motor include winding inductance and resistance as well pole pair and back-emf constant. The output of the brushless motor is connected via a Hall sensor to a mechanical load. The angular speed of the motor drive is displayed in the scope on the right side. Students first have to understand the typical wiring from the Hall sensors towards the control.

Fig. 8: Brushless motor drive using a virtual breadboard

The cross-section of the brushless motor in Fig.7 is animated during the simulation. The Hall signals coming from the Hall sensor are highlighted, depending on their logical state and the Conducting mosfets as well as the current path are coloured depending on the absolute value of the current. During the animation the rotor in the cross-section will rotate as well as the direction (indicated by the two arrows) of the applied winding flux from the stator. The students can visually inspect the dependency of the rotor position, Hall signals, control signals for the mosfets as well as the currents flowing through the motor windings. The scopes at the bottom left side of Fig 7. show the DC link current and line voltage between the first and second motor terminal. The current shows the typical rectangular blocks, while the line voltage shows the trapezoidal back-emf of the motor and the typical voltage spikes during commutation.

A simulation using a virtual breadboard with logic NAND and AND [3] is shown in Fig. 8. The angular speed of the motor is measured using a Tacho and displayed in

the digital multimeter. The Hall signals from the brushless motor are directly connected to the logic AND and NAND gates, that make the control signals for the mosfets. Since the PCB contains the required gate drivers for the mosfets, the outputs from the AND gates can directly be connected with the gating inputs of the PCB. A linear voltage regulator 7805 is applied to feed the logical gates [3].

The scope on the bottom right side shows the three Hall signals, while the other scope shows the voltage on the motor terminals from the voltage measurement terminals from the PCB.

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This Paper presents a result of the USB-(D)C initiative [5] in which USB type C technology is being developed. This project is funded by the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs. This result will also be available via the DCT-REES ERASMUS+ initiative, in which partners from EU and South-Africa work together to (re)develop educational materials towards a future DC-Grid. The pivotal role of Power Electronics for many different types of applications is described. The examples show how this experimental set up can be used to teach typical DC-DC applications, such as conversion and power exchange between two different DC voltages. Also the application of a grid-tied inverter and a PMDC and Brushless motor drive are demonstrated. Other applications that can be created using this PCB are Maximum Power Point trackers for solar cells, as well as battery chargers. In the case of motor drives the applications can be extended towards step motor control, unipolar and bipolar, full step half step and microstepping, bipolar and unipolar permanent magnet DC motor control as well as three phase trapezoidal brushless motor control and permanent magnet synchronous machine control using a digital controller. Analog control is directly connected to the voltage and current measurements terminals on the PCB and can control the mosfets using a natural sampling PWM modulation[4]. Digital control using a microcontroller can be added by connecting the measured signals to the analog inputs of the microcontroller, while the outputs from the microcontroller can drive the inputs of the gate drivers on the PCB.

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